

NAXSI Open-Source WAF

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2012 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20121213> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

WAF or *Web Application Firewall* is a fancy marketing name to describe technology that existed long before this term became common. In fact the technology behind WAF used to be called *full application reverse-proxy* and basically allows to forward, inspect and sanitize (or block) protocol requests to an application server.

Those servers are most of the time critical assets or positioned in critical zones and therefore needs an added layer of security. Beware that a WAF is not a magic thing that will solve all your problem in publishing a web application you always should apply to following security rules:

- Integrate threat risk model when designing applications (*The OWASP risk model* [1] is a good example)
- Review code of published applications
- Review implementation design (application communication, interfaces, ...)
- Secure middleware if any (Java, SQL, .NET, ...)
- Secure underlying operating system
- Review authentication and authorization of whole framework
- Check for the OWASP top 10 vulnerabilities before going public
- Do a penetration test of the environment before going live
- Deploy an anomaly detection system that will help when things starts to go wrong
- Last but not least: remember to log wisely and put those information in a safe place. You may need it when things went wrong.

WAF implementation in the security design makes also sense when all of the above rules have been followed, because it adds another layer of defense. Experience

teaches us that there is never enough defense when it comes to web application security.

3. Why using a WAF?

Usually you better have a WAF instance in place if you have to deal with a situation reflecting one or a combination of the following security issues regarding a web application:

- closed source and no possibility to inspect the source code
- vulnerabilities that cannot be fixed or mitigated on the system
- vulnerabilities that needs too much effort (costs) to be fixed
- too old to be patched
- too critical to be patched
- too complex to be secured efficiently
- authentication/authorization that is not available on the system

Maybe you'll find another one, but you get the point by now. *Virtual patching* is also a term used in such cases to describe one of the main feature of WAF: It allows to virtually patch a vulnerable web application, blocking the attack before it happens on the application proxy gateway.

You may argue that such attack may also affect the gateway itself (we are inspecting and interpreting the application protocol, remember?) and yes, WAF life is a dangerous one.

WAF configuring and fine tuning is not to be underestimated, that is why I told you before there is no magic thing that will do all for you from the start and stay forever that way – Remember: Security is a process.

4. Blacklisting vs. Whitelisting

Talking about WAF we need to distinguish two major categories of *modus operandi*: The blacklist and the whitelist approach (also referred as *positive and negative security model* [2]).

The blacklist approach tries to block all *bad* things based on blacklists done by you and/or pre-configured for you. The whitelist approach tries to define an allowed baseline of what is allowed to do with the web application. As you

may guess WAF can also take the hybrid approach to accomplish the following requirements:

- Protect from top 10 OWASP vulnerabilities
- Provide few *false positives*
- Provide no *false Negatives*
- Provide brute force protection
- Protect from XSS, SQL injection, CSRF and file inclusions
- Block *strange* characters an or requests
- Sanitize HTTP & XML requests

There are several good commercial product out there (like Airlock and others) that fulfill almost all requirements, but I like to talk about the open source project *NAXSI* [3].

5. NAXSI Project

The *NAXSI Project* is not so known like the *ModSecurity open source project* [4], but has a very interesting approach and features.

NAXSI uses the small and performant reverse proxy engine of Nginx web server instead of the full blown Apache engine used by ModSecurity (and from a security point of view: the lesser code).

Following are the major feature of NAXSI:

- Protects from XSS, SQL injections, CSRF, file inclusion
- Fast engine
- Relative simple configuration
- Check GET/POST requests
- Check HTTP headers and cookies
- Forbid *dangerous symbols and SQL keywords* [5]
- Allows whitelist approach configuration creating a web application baseline
- Able to run in learn or production mode
- Uses no signature of known attack

6. Installation

Let's do a quick installation with ubuntu sever 12.04 LTS. You may also install it from the sources following the *Nginx prerequisites* [6] for reference. After you've installed the basic server with openssh, install NAXSI with:

```
sudo apt-get install nginx-naxsi
```

7. Initial configuration

In the nginx configuration file (`/etc/nginx/nginx.conf`) uncomment this line to activate the basic rulesets:

```
##
# nginx-naxsi config
##
# Uncomment it if you installed nginx-naxsi
##
include /etc/nginx/naxsi_core.rules;
```

Note that this file is not an attack signature repository but rather a "score rules" set. Let's configure NAXSI for our website `www.scip.ch`. To do so edit the Nginx configuration file in `/etc/nginx/sites-enabled/default` and add following entries in the server context:

```
server {
    proxy_set_header Proxy-Connection "";
    listen 80;

    location / {
        # put your website IP here
        proxy_pass
        http://80.74.141.2/;

        # put your website FQDN here
        proxy_set_header Host
        www.scip.ch;

        # Uncomment to enable naxsi
        on this location
        include
        /etc/nginx/naxsi.rules;
    }

    # Only for nginx-naxsi : process
    denied requests
    location /RequestDenied {
        # For example, return an HTTP
        error code
        return 418;
    }
}
```

Now you should be able to start the nginx service that will bring up the NASXI with following command:

```
sudo service nginx start
```

Be sure to check for error messages on the console or in the error log found in `/var/log/nginx/error.log` and verify with `sudo netstat -antup` that nginx daemon is opening the configured port (tcp/80 in our case). The output should look like this:

```
Active Internet connections (servers and
established)
Proto Recv-Q Send-Q Local Address   Foreign
Address        State          PID/Program name
tcp            0      0 0.0.0.0:80      0.0.0.0:*
LISTEN         9865/nginx
tcp            0      0 0.0.0.0:22     0.0.0.0:*
LISTEN         8484/sshd
tcp            0      0 127.0.0.1:6010 0.0.0.0:*
LISTEN         9627/0
tcp            0      0 127.0.0.1:6011 0.0.0.0:*
LISTEN         9062/1
tcp            0      0 x.y.z.52:22    32 x.y.z.52:22
x.y.z.36:49749 ESTABLISHED 9046/sshd: anco
udp            0      0 0.0.0.0:68     0.0.0.0:*
649/dhclient3
```

To test if it works, start a browser session and point it to the ip address of your test server (`x.y.z.52:80`) and you should see the website you configured (`www.scip.ch`) in the config file above. To continue further testing make sure you will proxying all web request to the nginx-NAXSI WAF. To accomplish this you can either use the web-proxy configuration setting in the browser or *fake* the testing website ip address in your system hostfile. I prefer to put the ip address in my hostfile:

```
x.y.z.52    www.scip.ch
```

Here are the location of the target hosts file (you need admin right to save changes):

OS	Host Configuration File
Windows	%SYSTEMROOT%\system32\drivers\etc\hosts
Linux	/etc/hosts

Now we can browse to www.scip.ch and be sure that our test NAXSI WAF will inspect the content and remember that by now the configuration is in *learning mode*; it will only report errors in the nginx error logs (`/var/log/nginx/error.log`) and *not* block any bad scored request.

8. How It Works

The `naxsi_core.rules` are responsible for scoring the HTTP input and looks like this (excerpt):

```
MainRule "str:;" "msg:; in stuff"
"mz:BODY|URL|ARGS" "s:$SQL:4" id:1008;
#
MainRule "str:<" "msg:html open tag"
"mz:ARGS|URL|BODY|$HEADERS_VAR:Cookie"
"s:$XSS:8" id:1302;
#
MainRule "str:&#" "msg: utf7/8 encoding"
"mz:ARGS|BODY|URL|$HEADERS_VAR:Cookie"
"s:$EVADE:4" id:1400;
#
MainRule "rx:.php|.asp*" "msg:asp/php file
upload!" "mz:FILE_EXT" "s:$UPLOAD:8" id:1500;
```

Insight this file is the logic configuration used to score the input; the result will be used in `/etc/nginx/naxsi.rules` to decide if such input may be allowed or not. The format is quite simple:

1. Define what to look for: string (`str:`) or regular expression (`rx:`)
2. Define message to report into logfiles (`msg:`)
3. Put the rule a category (`s:`)
4. Assign rule identifier (`id:`)
5. Define where to look for (`mz:`) and short description below

mz entry	Look in
URL	URL path
ARGS	HTTP argument
BODY	HTML body entry
\$HEADERS_VAR:	HTTP header variable

Now let's take a look on the second NAXSI config file `/etc/nginx/naxsi.rules` where the main NAXSI behavior is defined; this is how it looks like:

```
# config mode section
LearningMode;
SecRulesEnabled;
#SecRulesDisabled;
DeniedUrl "/RequestDenied";
#
# check rules section
CheckRule "$SQL >= 8" BLOCK;
CheckRule "$RFI >= 8" BLOCK;
CheckRule "$TRAVERSAL >= 4" BLOCK;
```

```
CheckRule "$EVADE >= 4" BLOCK;
CheckRule "$XSS >= 8" BLOCK;
```

Here is an explanation of the contents:

1. `LearningMode` – activates learning mode; in this mode requests aren't blocked and white lists may be created.
2. `SecRulesEnabled` or `SecRulesDisabled` – to activate or disable NAXSI for this location/section.
3. `DeniedURL` – redirect URL for blocked requests; can be an HTTP error code (like 4xx or 5xx) or forward to an HTML site with code to help track false-positives.
4. `CheckRule` – per-category check scores; the score we saw above will be evaluated here. If a request hits a score in the `naxsi_core.rules`, this score will be recorded and added to each category (`SQL`, `XSS`, `EVADE`, ...) if the overall score for any of the categories is reached (8 in `SQL` per default) the input is treated as *bad*.

When you use the whitelist (positive secure model) approach you'll find also the white-list entries (`BasicRule` statement) in this config file:

```
# Whitelist '|', as it's used on the /report/
page, in argument 'd'
BasicRule wl:1005
"mz:$URL:/report/|$ARGS_VAR:d";
# Whitelist ',' on URL zone as it's massively
used for URL rewriting !
BasicRule wl:1008 "mz:URL";
```

The entry above will result in disabling some part of the check rule in `naxsi_core.rules` allowing a specific behavior and eliminate false-positives. `BasicRule` could be more or less specific at your pace (and security needs).

9. Information Gathering

At this stage we have our test installation inspecting the HTTP flow and reporting bad things in the `/var/log/nginx/error.log` file, let's take a look on how NAXSI error entry looks like:

```
> error.log <
2012/11/30 04:57:55 [error] 9866#0: *47
NAXSI_FMT:
ip=x.y.z.36&server=x.y.z.52&uri=/testmiztot&t
otal_processed=8589934625&total_blocked=67902
9381853280060&zone0=URL&id0=1999&var_name0=,
client:x.y.z.36, server: localhost, request:
"GET /testmiztot HTTP/1.1", host: "x.y.z.52"
```

As you can see it's a special error message: it was generated on a "special" HTTP URL GET request and is not a really bad request. To test the functionality on the WAF I've created this test-rule in the `/etc/nginx/naxsi_core.rules`:

```
MainRule "str:testmiztot" "msg:foobar test
pattern" "mz:URL" "s:$SQL:42" id:1999;
```

This rule will trigger whenever the `testmiztot` string is detected in the address part (`mz:URL`) of the HTTP GET request and score as 42 (`s:$SQL:42`) in the `SQL` category. This will be evaluated as *bad* because the `SQL` category limit is 8. The `msg:` text will be shown in the learning mode log used to generate the white-list baseline.

10. Summary

NAXSI is open source, high performance, low rules maintenance, and uses the very good Nginx reverse-proxy engine. Still, Naxsi is young, and there are *known bugs* [7]. So test it, use it and see if it can help in your environment.

11. External Links

- [1] https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Threat_Risk_Modeling
- [2] https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Positive_security_model
- [3] <http://code.google.com/p/naxsi>
- [4] <http://www.modsecurity.org>
- [5] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20110914>
- [6] <http://code.google.com/p/naxsi/wiki/Howto>
- [7] <http://code.google.com/p/naxsi/wiki/KnownBugs>